

Arithmetically Exact Wilson–Dirac Operator Coupled to $U(1)$ on Cyclotomic Groups G_N

(Coefficients in $\mathbb{Z}[\zeta_N]$, IEEE-754-free computation, structural validation in 1D and 2D,
and spectral analysis)

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Abstract

We construct the Euclidean Wilson–Dirac operator coupled to a $U(1)$ gauge field on periodic lattices $\Lambda_B^d = (\mathbb{Z}/B\mathbb{Z})^d$, where the gauge links belong to the discrete subgroup $G_N = \{\zeta_N^k\}_{k \in \mathbb{Z}/N\mathbb{Z}} \subset U(1)$ with $\zeta_N = e^{2\pi i/N}$. The operator coefficients are elements of the cyclotomic ring $R_N = \mathbb{Z}[\zeta_N] \cong \mathbb{Z}[x]/(\Phi_N(x))$, and the field amplitudes belong to $M_{s,N} = \frac{1}{s}R_N$. For $4 \mid N$ the Euclidean matrices Γ_μ and Γ_5 in the Dirac–Pauli representation have coefficients in R_N , and the gauge links belong to R_N^\times .

We prove: (i) a well-defined output scale of the coupled Wilson–Dirac operator, (ii) zero arithmetic error $E_{\text{arith}} = 0$ (all operations reduce to integer arithmetic and reduction modulo Φ_N), (iii) gauge covariance with respect to G_N , (iv) Γ_5 -hermiticity $\Gamma_5 D_{W,U} \Gamma_5 = D_{W,U}^\dagger$, (v) an explicit bound on the approximation error of general $U(1)$ by G_N of order $\mathcal{O}(\sin(\pi/N))$. We also analyse the cost of reduction modulo Φ_N as a function of $\varphi(N)$.

The empirical part is based on the script `experiments3.py` (Python 3.14.5, NumPy 2.5.0, SciPy 1.18.0, `seed=1234`). We present experiments validating: gauge covariance and Γ_5 -hermiticity (positive and negative tests) in 1D and 2D, asymptotic scaling of multiplication complexity (averaged over 3 seeds, range $N \in \{4, \dots, 1024\}$), timing scaling $T \sim B^d$ for $d = 1, 2$, convergence of the gauge error $\sim \sin(\pi/N)$, spectral analysis (Γ_5 -residual in the correct Euclidean metric $|\lambda - \bar{\lambda}|$, Wilson doubler suppression with an analytic derivation of the doubler count and minimal mass, comparison with the analytic free-field spectrum), and growth of coefficient bit-length in iterated operator applications as well as in comparison with an RLWE-style multiplication chain. Results are bit-identical across platforms (Windows/Python 3.14.5 and Linux/Python 3.12), providing an independent confirmation of $E_{\text{arith}} = 0$.

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1 Introduction

We consider a discrete fermionic theory on a periodic lattice, in which the standard gauge links $U_\mu(x) \in U(1)$ are replaced by the discrete subgroup $G_N \subset U(1)$, and the numerical coefficients are maintained in the cyclotomic ring $R_N = \mathbb{Z}[\zeta_N]$. The goal is a formalism in which evaluation of the Wilson–Dirac operator is performed without rounding errors ($E_{\text{arith}} = 0$).

Remark 1.1 (Meaning of exactness). Exactness here means the absence of floating-point arithmetic errors. We do not claim that the model automatically yields a practically cheap solver for large systems — the empirical part reveals a limitation in the form of rapid growth of number sizes in iterated operator applications.

Remark 1.2 (Scope). We analyse $U(1)$ gauging approximated by G_N . Extension to non-abelian groups (e.g. $SU(2)$, $SU(3)$) requires a separate construction and is not addressed here.

Organisation. Section 2 defines the ring R_N and the group G_N . Section 3 discusses Dirac matrices over R_N . Section 4 introduces the lattice and the inner product. Section 5 defines $D_{W,U}$ and proves the basic algebraic properties. Sections 6 and 7 are devoted to covariance and Γ_5 -hermiticity. Section 8 analyses the approximation error $U(1) \rightarrow G_N$. Section 9 discusses arithmetic complexity. Section 10 presents the empirical results.

2 Cyclotomic Rings and Discrete $U(1)$

2.1 The Ring R_N and Conjugation

Definition 2.1 (Cyclotomic ring). Let $N \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$ and $\zeta_N := e^{2\pi i/N}$. Define

$$R_N := \mathbb{Z}[\zeta_N] \cong \mathbb{Z}[x]/(\Phi_N(x)), \quad K_N := \mathbb{Q}(\zeta_N),$$

where Φ_N is the N -th cyclotomic polynomial.

Definition 2.2 (Complex conjugation). The involution $*$: $K_N \rightarrow K_N$ defined by $\zeta_N^* := \zeta_N^{-1} = \overline{\zeta_N}$, extended \mathbb{Q} -linearly. For $\alpha \in K_N$ we write $\alpha^* = \bar{\alpha}$ interchangeably.

Lemma 2.1 (Closure). For $a, b \in R_N$: $ab \in R_N$ and $\bar{a} \in R_N$.

Proof. R_N is a ring, so $ab \in R_N$. Since $\zeta_N^{-1} = \zeta_N^{N-1} \in R_N$, conjugating a polynomial in ζ_N yields a polynomial in ζ_N^{-1} , so $\bar{a} \in R_N$. \square

2.2 The Discrete Gauge Group G_N

Definition 2.3 (Gauge group).

$$G_N := \{\zeta_N^k : k \in \mathbb{Z}/N\mathbb{Z}\} \subset U(1).$$

Lemma 2.2 (Unitarity and conjugation). For $u \in G_N$: $u \in R_N^\times$ and $u^{-1} = \bar{u} \in G_N$.

Proof. For $u = \zeta_N^k$: $u^{-1} = \zeta_N^{-k} = \bar{u} \in G_N$ and $u \cdot u^{-1} = 1$, so u is a unit in R_N . \square

2.3 The Condition $4 \mid N$ and the Family $N = 2^k$

Lemma 2.3 ($i \in K_N$). $i \in K_N$ if and only if $4 \mid N$. In that case $i = \zeta_N^{N/4} \in R_N$.

Proof. If $4 \mid N$, then $\zeta_N^{N/4} = e^{i\pi/2} = i$. Conversely: $i \in \mathbb{Q}(\zeta_N) \iff \mathbb{Q}(i) \subseteq \mathbb{Q}(\zeta_N) \iff 4 \mid N$. \square

Remark 2.1 (The family $N = 2^k$). For $N = 2^k$ ($k \geq 2$): $\Phi_N(x) = x^{\varphi(N)} + 1$ (negacyclic), $\varphi(N) = N/2$, $4 \mid N$ always holds, elements of G_N are monomials $\pm x^j$, and multiplication by a link costs $\mathcal{O}(\varphi(N))$ instead of $\mathcal{O}(\varphi(N)^2)$. This family is the basis of the implementation described in Section 10.

3 Dirac Matrices: Euclidean Convention over R_N

Definition 3.1 (Euclidean matrices). Let γ^μ be the standard Dirac–Pauli matrices. Define the Hermitian Euclidean matrices:

$$\Gamma_k := i\gamma^k, \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \quad \Gamma_4 := \gamma^0.$$

For $d \leq 4$ we use Γ_μ , $\mu = 1, \dots, d$.

Lemma 3.1 (Entries and Clifford relations). *If $4 \mid N$, then the entries of Γ_μ belong to R_N and:*

$$\Gamma_\mu^\dagger = \Gamma_\mu, \quad \{\Gamma_\mu, \Gamma_\nu\} = 2\delta_{\mu\nu}\mathbb{1}_4.$$

Proof. The entries of γ^μ belong to $\{0, \pm 1, \pm i\}$; for $4 \mid N$ we have $i = \zeta_N^{N/4} \in R_N$ (Lemma 2.3). Hermiticity and anti-commutation follow from the Euclidean construction $\Gamma_k = i\gamma^k$, $\Gamma_4 = \gamma^0$. \square

Definition 3.2 (Chiral matrix). $\Gamma_5 := \Gamma_1\Gamma_2\Gamma_3\Gamma_4$.

Lemma 3.2 (Properties of Γ_5). $\Gamma_5^\dagger = \Gamma_5$, $\Gamma_5^2 = \mathbb{1}_4$, $\{\Gamma_5, \Gamma_\mu\} = 0$ for $\mu = 1, \dots, 4$.

Proof. Standard properties of the Clifford algebra in Euclidean signature. \square

In the Dirac–Pauli representation used in the implementation ($d \leq 2$) the action of the matrices on a spinor $(\psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3, \psi_4)$ reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_1 &: (i\psi_4, i\psi_3, -i\psi_2, -i\psi_1), \\ \Gamma_2 &: (\psi_4, -\psi_3, -\psi_2, \psi_1), \\ \Gamma_5 &: \text{diag}(+1, +1, -1, -1). \end{aligned}$$

Each row of Γ_μ has exactly one nonzero entry of modulus 1, so $C_\Gamma := \max_\mu \|\Gamma_\mu\|_\infty = 1$.

4 Lattice, Fields, and Inner Product

Definition 4.1 (Periodic lattice). For $B \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$ and $d \geq 1$:

$$\Lambda_B^d := (\mathbb{Z}/B\mathbb{Z})^d, \quad h := \frac{1}{B}.$$

We denote by $\hat{\mu}$ the unit vector in direction μ .

Definition 4.2 (Value scales). $M_{s,N} := \{a/s : a \in R_N\} \subset K_N$ for $s \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$.

Definition 4.3 (Spinor field). A spinor field is a function $\Psi : \Lambda_B^d \rightarrow (M_{s,N})^4$.

Definition 4.4 (Inner product and adjoint).

$$\langle \Psi, \Phi \rangle := \sum_{x \in \Lambda_B^d} \Psi(x)^\dagger \Phi(x),$$

where \dagger denotes conjugation $*$ and transposition (cf. Definition 2.2). The adjoint A^\dagger of an operator A is defined by $\langle \Psi, A\Phi \rangle = \langle A^\dagger\Psi, \Phi \rangle$.

Notation 4.1 (Analytic norm). In estimates we use the embedding $\iota : K_N \hookrightarrow \mathbb{C}$, $\iota(\zeta_N) = e^{2\pi i/N}$, and the norm $\|v\|_\infty := \max_j |\iota(v_j)|$. This is an analytic tool, not a computational one.

5 The Coupled Wilson–Dirac Operator

Definition 5.1 (Gauge links). $U_\mu : \Lambda_B^d \rightarrow G_N$, $\mu = 1, \dots, d$.

Definition 5.2 (Naive Dirac operator). For $m \in M_{s_m, N}$:

$$(D_U \Psi)(x) := \sum_{\mu=1}^d \Gamma_\mu \frac{U_\mu(x) \Psi(x + \hat{\mu}) - \overline{U_\mu(x - \hat{\mu})} \Psi(x - \hat{\mu})}{2h} + m \Psi(x).$$

Definition 5.3 (Wilson term and $D_{W,U}$). For $r \in M_{s_r, N}$:

$$(W_U \Psi)(x) := -\frac{r}{2h} \sum_{\mu=1}^d \left(U_\mu(x) \Psi(x + \hat{\mu}) - 2\Psi(x) + \overline{U_\mu(x - \hat{\mu})} \Psi(x - \hat{\mu}) \right),$$

$$D_{W,U} := D_U + W_U.$$

Notation 5.1 (Parity factor). $\delta_B := 2 / \gcd(2, B) \in \{1, 2\}$.

Theorem 5.1 (Output scale). Let $4 \mid N$, $\Psi \in (M_{s_\psi, N})^4$, $m \in M_{s_m, N}$, $r \in M_{s_r, N}$. Then $(D_{W,U} \Psi)(x) \in (M_{s_{\text{out}}, N})^4$, where

$$s_{\text{out}} = s_\psi \cdot \text{lcm}(\delta_B, s_m, \delta_B s_r).$$

Proof. The factor $1/(2h) = B/2$ introduces a denominator of 2 only for odd B , encoded by δ_B . Multiplications by $U_\mu \in G_N \subset R_N^\times$ and by $\Gamma_\mu \in \text{Mat}_4(R_N)$ introduce no new denominators. The common denominator arises from combining: the kinetic part $(\delta_B s_\psi)$, the mass term $(s_m s_\psi)$, and the Wilson term $(\delta_B s_r s_\psi)$. \square

Theorem 5.2 (Zero arithmetic error). For $4 \mid N$, evaluation of $D_{W,U} \Psi$ can be performed using only integer arithmetic in $R_N \cong \mathbb{Z}[x]/(\Phi_N(x))$, so $E_{\text{arith}} = 0$.

Proof. All operations $(+, \times, \text{reduction modulo } \Phi_N)$ act on lists of integer coefficients without any floating-point operations. Correctness is confirmed by a deterministic SHA-256 hash of the result: invoking the computation twice on the same input yields an identical result for all tested N (Section 10.3). Furthermore, results are bit-identical across two independent platforms (Windows/Python 3.14.5 and Linux/Python 3.12), providing external confirmation of the absence of floating-point dependence. \square

6 Gauge Covariance

Definition 6.1 (Gauge transformation). For $g : \Lambda_B^d \rightarrow G_N$:

$$\Psi^g(x) := g(x) \Psi(x), \quad U_\mu^g(x) := g(x) U_\mu(x) \overline{g(x + \hat{\mu})}.$$

Theorem 6.1 (Covariance). $D_{W,U^g} \Psi^g = (D_{W,U} \Psi)^g$.

Proof. $U_\mu^g(x) \Psi^g(x + \hat{\mu}) = g(x) U_\mu(x) \underbrace{\overline{g(x + \hat{\mu})} g(x + \hat{\mu})}_{=1} \Psi(x + \hat{\mu}) = g(x) U_\mu(x) \Psi(x + \hat{\mu})$. The backward step and the Wilson term are handled analogously. The mass term commutes with $g(x)$ (scalar multiplication). \square

7 Γ_5 -Hermiticity

Lemma 7.1 (Adjoint of transport). *For the operators $T_{\mu,+}\Psi(x) := U_\mu(x)\Psi(x + \hat{\mu})$ and $T_{\mu,-}\Psi(x) := \overline{U_\mu(x - \hat{\mu})}\Psi(x - \hat{\mu})$ we have $T_{\mu,+}^\dagger = T_{\mu,-}$.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Psi, T_{\mu,+}\Phi \rangle &= \sum_x \Psi(x)^\dagger U_\mu(x) \Phi(x + \hat{\mu}) \\ &= \sum_y (\overline{U_\mu(y - \hat{\mu})} \Psi(y - \hat{\mu}))^\dagger \Phi(y) = \langle T_{\mu,-}\Psi, \Phi \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 7.1 (Γ_5 -hermiticity). *If $\overline{m} = m$ and $\overline{r} = r$, then $\Gamma_5 D_{W,U} \Gamma_5 = D_{W,U}^\dagger$.*

Proof. The difference operator $\nabla_\mu^U := (T_{\mu,+} - T_{\mu,-})/(2h)$ is anti-Hermitian (Lemma 7.1). Since Γ_μ is Hermitian and $\{\Gamma_5, \Gamma_\mu\} = 0$:

$$\Gamma_5 (\Gamma_\mu \nabla_\mu^U) \Gamma_5 = -\Gamma_\mu \Gamma_5 \nabla_\mu^U \Gamma_5 = \Gamma_\mu (\nabla_\mu^U)^\dagger.$$

The Wilson term W_U is Hermitian and $[\Gamma_5, W_U] = 0$, so $\Gamma_5 W_U \Gamma_5 = W_U^\dagger$. The mass term $m \mathbb{1}$ is self-adjoint when $\overline{m} = m$. □

Remark 7.1 (Spectral implication). Theorem 7.1 implies a symmetry of the spectrum of $D_{W,U}$ in Euclidean signature. If $D_{W,U}v = \lambda v$, then from $\Gamma_5 D_{W,U} \Gamma_5 = D_{W,U}^\dagger$ it follows that $D_{W,U}^\dagger(\Gamma_5 v) = \lambda(\Gamma_5 v)$, hence $D_{W,U}(\Gamma_5 v) = \overline{\lambda}(\Gamma_5 v)$, so

$$\lambda \in \text{spec}(D_{W,U}) \implies \overline{\lambda} \in \text{spec}(D_{W,U}).$$

The spectrum is symmetric with respect to the real axis (not the imaginary axis, as in Minkowski signature). The correct metric for this symmetry is therefore $|\lambda_j - \overline{\lambda_{k(j)}}|$, not $|\lambda_j + \overline{\lambda_{k(j)}}|$.

Remark 7.2 (Necessity of the conditions). Experiments (Section 10.3) show that a purely imaginary mass ($m = i = \zeta_N^{N/4}$, violating $\overline{m} = m$) consistently breaks Γ_5 -hermiticity (250/250 negative tests in 1D, 120/120 in 2D), suggesting that the condition $\overline{m} = m$ is not only sufficient but also necessary.

8 Approximation of $U(1)$ by G_N and Discretisation Error

Definition 8.1 (Phase quantisation). For $u = e^{i\theta} \in U(1)$: $Q_N(u) := \zeta_N^{k^*}$, where $k^* = \arg \min_{k \in \mathbb{Z}/N\mathbb{Z}} |\theta - 2\pi k/N|$.

Lemma 8.1 (Single-link error). *For every $u \in U(1)$: $|u - Q_N(u)| \leq 2 \sin(\pi/N)$.*

Proof. The maximum phase error is π/N ; the chord of an arc with half-angle π/N on the unit circle has length $2 \sin(\pi/N)$. □

Theorem 8.1 (Operator error from quantisation). *For the kinetic part, pointwise:*

$$\|(D_U - D_{Q_N(U)})\Psi(x)\|_\infty \leq \frac{B}{2} \cdot 4d C_\Gamma \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{N}\right) \cdot \max_{y=x \pm \hat{\mu}} \|\Psi(y)\|_\infty, \quad C_\Gamma = 1.$$

Proof. The difference $D_U - D_{Q_N(U)}$ arises from replacing $U_\mu(x) \rightarrow Q_N(U_\mu(x))$; the difference on each link is bounded by $2 \sin(\pi/N)$ (Lemma 8.1). In each direction μ there are two links ($\pm \hat{\mu}$), $\|\Gamma_\mu\|_\infty = C_\Gamma = 1$, and the factor $B/2$ comes from $1/(2h)$. Summing over $2d$ links gives the factor $4d \cdot C_\Gamma \cdot \sin(\pi/N)$. □

9 Arithmetic Complexity in R_N

Proposition 9.1 (Cost of multiplication in R_N). *Multiplication of two arbitrary elements of R_N by the naive algorithm (negacyclic convolution) costs $\mathcal{O}(\varphi(N)^2)$ coefficient operations. For $N = 2^k$ and elements of G_N (monomials $\pm x^j$) multiplication costs $\mathcal{O}(\varphi(N))$.*

Justification. Negacyclic convolution of length $n = \varphi(N)$: n^2 multiplications and n^2 additions in \mathbb{Z} . A monomial $\pm x^s$ has one nonzero coefficient; multiplication amounts to reindexing the array with a sign change at positions exceeding n (using $x^n = -1$): cost $\mathcal{O}(n)$. \square

Remark 9.1 (Empirical asymptotics). Experiments for $N \in \{4, 8, \dots, 1024\}$ ($\varphi \in \{2, \dots, 512\}$, averaged over 3 seeds) give asymptotic slopes (upper half of the range: $\varphi = 64, \dots, 512$): **2.07** for general multiplication and **0.98** for monomial multiplication, consistent with Proposition 9.1. Full-range slopes (1.85 and 0.87) are reduced by Python interpreter overhead dominating at small $\varphi \leq 8$.

10 Empirical Results

10.1 Experimental Conditions

All results come from a single run of the script `experiments3.py`. The script generates random data at `seed=1234`, executes seven experiment sets (EXP 1–EXP 7), prints tables to the console, and saves plots to the directory `plots_v3/`. The full console log is available in the file `run_log.txt` accompanying this submission.

Environment. Windows 10 (10.0.19045), Python 3.14.5 (64-bit, MSC v.1944), NumPy 2.5.0, SciPy 1.18.0, `seed=1234`.

Comparative models.

- **exact:** Python implementation (`int` lists; operations in R_N exact, monomial multiplication $\mathcal{O}(\varphi)$),
- **float/numpy:** `complex128` NumPy (C vectorisation; performance baseline).

10.2 EXP 1: Multiplication Complexity in R_N

For $N \in \{4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024\}$ ($\varphi \in \{2, \dots, 512\}$) micro-benchmark multiplication times were measured, averaged over 3 random seeds.

Log-log fit: full-range slope 1.85 (general) and 0.87 (monomial); asymptotic slope (upper half of the range) **2.07** and **0.98**, consistent with the theoretical $\mathcal{O}(\varphi^2)$ and $\mathcal{O}(\varphi)$.

10.3 EXP 1B: Structural Tests in 1D

For $B = 64$ and $N \in \{4, 8, 16, 32, 64\}$, 50 random instances were generated and the following identities were checked empirically:

$$D_{W,U^g} \Psi^g = (D_{W,U} \Psi)^g, \quad \Gamma_5 D_{W,U} \Gamma_5 = D_{W,U}^\dagger.$$

Negative tests: (i) incorrect gauge link transformation (using $g(x + \hat{\mu})$ instead of $\overline{g(x + \hat{\mu})}$, yielding $U_{\text{wrong}}^g(x) = g(x)U_\mu(x)g(x + \hat{\mu})$ instead of $g(x)U_\mu(x)\overline{g(x + \hat{\mu})}$), (ii) purely imaginary mass ($m = \zeta_N^{N/4} = i$, violating the condition $\bar{m} = m$ of Theorem 7.1).

All 250 positive tests and 500 negative tests passed as expected. The deterministic SHA-256 hash of the result gave identical values on two successive invocations for every N — confirming $E_{\text{arith}} = 0$.

Table 1: EXP 1: multiplication times vs $\varphi(N) = N/2$ (averaged over 3 seeds).

N	φ	$t_{\text{mul,gen}}$ [s]	$t_{\text{mul,mono}}$ [s]
4	2	2.07e-06	9.00e-07
8	4	4.57e-06	1.40e-06
16	8	1.36e-05	2.53e-06
32	16	4.65e-05	3.97e-06
64	32	1.68e-04	7.50e-06
128	64	6.36e-04	1.34e-05
256	128	2.56e-03	2.66e-05
512	256	1.14e-02	5.32e-05
1024	512	5.09e-02	1.12e-04

Figure 1: EXP 1: multiplication times vs $\varphi(N)$ (averaged over 3 seeds, range $N = 4 \dots 1024$). Left panel: full range with $O(n)$ and $O(n^2)$ references. Right panel: asymptotic fit (upper half of the range) — slopes 2.07 and 0.98 consistent with theory.

Table 2: EXP 1B: structural tests in 1D ($B = 64$, 50 trials per N). NEG columns: violations detected / 50 (expected: all). Column det: SHA-256 hash verification ($E_{\text{arith}} = 0$).

N	φ	Covariance	Γ_5 -herm.	NEG: wrong tr.	NEG: im. mass	det
4	2	50/50	50/50	50/50	50/50	OK
8	4	50/50	50/50	50/50	50/50	OK
16	8	50/50	50/50	50/50	50/50	OK
32	16	50/50	50/50	50/50	50/50	OK
64	32	50/50	50/50	50/50	50/50	OK

10.4 EXP 2: 1D Timing Scaling ($T \sim B$)

For $N = 64$ and $B \in \{16, 32, 64, 128, 256\}$, the time for a single operator application was measured.

Table 3: EXP 2: scaling in B (1D, $N = 64$).

B	t_{exact} [s]	t_{np} [s]	t_{ex}/B [s]	t_{np}/B [s]	ratio	bitlen
16	2.807e-03	1.133e-04	1.754e-04	7.084e-06	24.8	8
32	5.739e-03	1.242e-04	1.793e-04	3.883e-06	46.2	9
64	1.187e-02	1.168e-04	1.855e-04	1.824e-06	101.7	10
128	2.294e-02	1.361e-04	1.792e-04	1.063e-06	168.6	11
256	4.801e-02	1.546e-04	1.875e-04	6.041e-07	310.4	12

Empirical slope: $t_{\text{exact}} \sim B^{1.02}$ (target $\sim B^1$). The time per site (t/B) is constant in the range $1.75\text{--}1.88 \times 10^{-4}$ s — confirming locality. The `bitlen` column grows by ≈ 1 bit per doubling of B , arising from the factor $B/2$ in the operator.

10.5 EXP 3: 2D Scaling ($T \sim B^2$) and Structural Tests in 2D

For $N = 64$ and $B \in \{8, 16, 24, 32\}$ we simultaneously: (a) measured the timing of the 2D operator application, (b) ran 30 random trials of structural tests (covariance and Γ_5 -hermiticity) in 2D together with negative tests.

Table 4: EXP 3: 2D scaling and structural tests ($N = 64$, 30 trials per B). Column NEG: total negative tests (covariance + Γ_5), expected: 60/60.

B	sites	t_{ex} [s]	t_{np} [s]	t_{ex}/B^2 [s]	Cov.	Γ_5	NEG
8	64	2.172e-02	2.859e-04	3.393e-04	30/30	30/30	60/60
16	256	8.744e-02	3.136e-04	3.416e-04	30/30	30/30	60/60
24	576	1.994e-01	4.151e-04	3.462e-04	30/30	30/30	60/60
32	1024	3.459e-01	5.779e-04	3.378e-04	30/30	30/30	60/60

Empirical slope: $t_{\text{exact}} \sim (B^2)^{1.00}$ (target ~ 1). Time per site $\approx 3.4 \times 10^{-4}$ s is constant. Structural tests: 120/120 positive and 240/240 negative — covariance and Γ_5 -hermiticity confirmed in 2D with the same confidence as in 1D.

10.6 EXP 4: Gauge Discretisation Error

We measured $E_{\text{gauge}} := \max_x \|(D_U - D_{Q_N(U)})\Psi(x)\|_\infty$ with a normalised field $\|\Psi\|_\infty = 1$.

Dependence on N (fixed $B = 64$). Empirical slope: $E_{\text{gauge}} \sim \sin(\pi/N)^{1.02}$ (target ~ 1 , Theorem 8.1). The ratio is 0.26–0.33, meaning the bound is conservative by a factor of $\approx 3\text{--}4$.

Dependence on B (fixed $N = 64$). Empirical slope: $E_{\text{gauge}} \sim B^{0.99}$ (target ~ 1). The ratio E_{gauge}/B lies in the range 0.030–0.043, confirming linear dependence on B . Variability of the ratio (0.30–0.44) arises from the randomness of the field Ψ and the link phases.

EXP 2+3: Operator timing

Figure 2: EXP 2+3: operator application time vs number of sites. Left panel: 1D ($T \sim B^{1.02}$). Right panel: 2D ($T \sim (B^2)^{1.00}$). Time per site is constant — confirming locality.

Table 5: EXP 4A: discretisation error vs N ($B = 64$). Bound: $\frac{B}{2} \cdot 4d C_{\Gamma} \sin(\pi/N) = 128 \sin(\pi/N)$ for $d = 1$, $C_{\Gamma} = 1$.

N	φ	$\sin(\pi/N)$	E_{gauge}	bound	ratio
4	2	7.0711e-01	2.917e+01	9.051e+01	0.322
8	4	3.8268e-01	1.407e+01	4.898e+01	0.287
16	8	1.9509e-01	6.883e+00	2.497e+01	0.276
32	16	9.8017e-02	4.166e+00	1.255e+01	0.332
64	32	4.9068e-02	1.978e+00	6.281e+00	0.315
128	64	2.4541e-02	8.262e-01	3.141e+00	0.263

Table 6: EXP 4B: discretisation error vs B ($N = 64$).

B	E_{gauge}	bound	ratio	E_{gauge}/B
16	5.951e-01	1.570e+00	0.379	3.719e-02
32	1.387e+00	3.140e+00	0.442	4.335e-02
64	1.898e+00	6.281e+00	0.302	2.965e-02
128	4.588e+00	1.256e+01	0.365	3.584e-02
256	1.014e+01	2.512e+01	0.404	3.961e-02

Table 7: EXP 5: growth of coefficient bit-length.

k	$\text{bitlen}(D^k\Psi)$	$\max c (D)$	$\text{bitlen}((D^\dagger D)^k\Psi)$	$\max c (D^\dagger D)$
0	2	3	2	3
1	10	576	16	49152
2	17	71680	30	8.05e+08
4	30	1.02e+09	58	2.15e+17
8	58	2.44e+17	114	1.49e+34
16	114	1.40e+34	226	6.91e+67
32	226	6.51e+67	450	1.53e+135
64	449	1.37e+135	897	8.56e+269

EXP 4: Gauge discretization error

Figure 3: EXP 4: gauge discretisation error $U(1) \rightarrow G_N$. Left panel: vs $\sin(\pi/N)$ at $B = 64$ — slope 1.02. Right panel: vs B at $N = 64$ — slope 0.99. Dashed lines: bound from Theorem 8.1.

10.7 EXP 5: Bit-Length Growth in Iterated Applications

We iterated $\Psi_{k+1} = D_{W,U}\Psi_k$ and $\Psi_{k+1} = D_{W,U}^\dagger D_{W,U}\Psi_k$ for $B = 64$, $N = 64$, $r = 1$, $m = 0$.

The pattern is regular: each application of D adds ≈ 7 bits (factor $B/2 = 32 \approx 5$ bits plus ≈ 2 bits from summing neighbouring sites). For $D^\dagger D$ the growth is twice as fast (≈ 14 bits/step). The bit-length sequence is bit-identical across platforms (Windows/Python 3.14.5 and Linux/Python 3.12), providing an independent confirmation of $E_{\text{arith}} = 0$.

Figure 4: EXP 5: growth of the maximum coefficient bit-length in iterated applications of D and $D^\dagger D$ ($N = 64$, $B = 64$, $r = 1$, $m = 0$).

Remark 10.1 (Practical limitation). $E_{\text{arith}} = 0$ for a single evaluation does not imply scalability of long iterations. Without size-control mechanisms (rescaling, modular arithmetic, CRT) the cost of integer multiplications grows rapidly with the coefficient bit-length. A comparison with bit-length growth in an RLWE-style multiplication chain is presented in Section 10.9.

10.8 EXP 6: Spectral Analysis — Γ_5 Spectrum Symmetry and Doubler Suppression

For $B \in \{8, 12, 16\}$, $N = 64$, and $r \in \{0.0, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0\}$ the full operator matrix (dimension $4B \times 4B$) was constructed via the IEEE-754 float embedding and eigenvalues were computed (`scipy.linalg.eigvals`).

Remark 10.2 (Methodological note). EXP 6 uses the IEEE-754 embedding (`complex128`) solely for spectral analysis. The algebraic property $\Gamma_5 D \Gamma_5 = D^\dagger$ is verified exactly in the exact model by the tests of Sections 10.3 and 10.5.

Metric for Γ_5 spectral symmetry. By Remark 7.1, Γ_5 -hermiticity in Euclidean signature implies spectrum symmetry about the real axis:

$$\lambda \in \text{spec}(D_{W,U}) \implies \bar{\lambda} \in \text{spec}(D_{W,U}).$$

For each eigenvalue λ_j we find the partner $\lambda_{k(j)}$ minimising $|\lambda_j - \bar{\lambda}_k|$ by a greedy matching sorted by $|\text{Im}(\lambda)|$. We report the absolute residual

$$\varepsilon_{\text{abs}} := \text{mean}_j |\lambda_j - \overline{\lambda_{k(j)}}|$$

and the relative residual

$$\varepsilon_{\text{rel}} := \text{mean}_j \frac{|\lambda_j - \overline{\lambda_{k(j)}}|}{|\lambda_j|}.$$

Table 8: EXP 6: Γ_5 spectral residual (absolute ε_{abs}) for trivial links ($U = 1$) and random links ($U \in U(1)$). All values at the level of machine precision $\varepsilon_{\text{mach}} \approx 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$, independently of r .

r	$U = 1$ (free field)		U random	
	$\varepsilon_{\text{abs}}, B = 8$	$\varepsilon_{\text{abs}}, B = 16$	$\varepsilon_{\text{abs}}, B = 8$	$\varepsilon_{\text{abs}}, B = 16$
0.0	3.19e-15	1.56e-14	4.73e-15	1.83e-14
0.5	6.17e-15	3.25e-14	9.46e-15	2.18e-14
1.0	1.38e-14	2.40e-14	1.03e-14	3.55e-14
2.0	1.63e-14	5.58e-14	2.74e-14	6.74e-14

Remark 10.3 (Interpretation of residuals). Absolute residuals $\varepsilon_{\text{abs}} \sim 10^{-15}$ – 10^{-14} for all $r \in \{0, 0.5, 1, 2\}$ and both link configurations confirm Γ_5 -hermiticity spectrally at machine precision. The relative residual ε_{rel} for $U = 1$ is $\sim 10^{-1}$ – 10^{-2} rather than $\varepsilon_{\text{mach}}$, because eigenvalues at $p_0 = 0$ satisfy $\lambda \approx 0$, causing numerical instability in the relative metric (division by $|\lambda| \approx 0$). This is a numerical artefact, not a violation of the algebraic property. For random U the artefact does not occur and $\varepsilon_{\text{rel}} \sim 10^{-15}$ for all r .

Comparison with the analytic spectrum. For the free field ($U \equiv 1, m = 0$) the eigenvalues of the 1D operator have the analytic form:

$$\lambda_{k,\pm} = rB(1 - \cos p_k) \pm iB \sin p_k, \quad p_k = \frac{2\pi k}{B}, \quad k = 0, \dots, B-1,$$

each with spinor multiplicity 2. Note that $\overline{\lambda_{k,+}} = \lambda_{k,-}$, which is an explicit manifestation of the symmetry $\lambda \in \text{spec}(D) \implies \bar{\lambda} \in \text{spec}(D)$ (Remark 7.1). The numerical error between the computed and analytic spectra is $\varepsilon_{\text{an}} \sim 10^{-14}$ – 10^{-13} (machine precision), confirming the correctness of the implementation.

Wilson doubler suppression. We define doubler modes as eigenvalues satisfying $|\text{Re}(\lambda)| > rB/2$. Using the analytic spectrum, this condition becomes:

$$rB(1 - \cos p_k) > \frac{rB}{2} \iff \cos p_k < \frac{1}{2} \iff p_k \in \left(\frac{\pi}{3}, \frac{5\pi}{3}\right).$$

Table 9: EXP 6: numerical error relative to the analytic spectrum ($U = 1$, $m = 0$) and doubler count and minimal mass. Doubler threshold: $|\operatorname{Re}(\lambda)| > rB/2$.

r	B	ε_{an}	n_{doublers}	$\min \operatorname{Re}(\lambda) _{\text{d}}$
0.0	8	1.07e-14	0	—
0.5	8	1.83e-14	20	4.000
1.0	8	6.21e-14	20	8.000
2.0	8	1.17e-13	20	16.000
0.0	16	6.04e-14	0	—
0.5	16	9.29e-14	44	4.939
1.0	16	8.62e-14	44	9.877
2.0	16	3.20e-13	44	19.754

The smallest lattice momentum $p_{k^*} = 2\pi k^*/B$ exceeding $\pi/3$ corresponds to

$$k^* = \left\lceil \frac{B}{6} \right\rceil,$$

so the minimal doubler mass is:

$$m_{W,\min} = rB \left(1 - \cos \frac{2\pi \lceil B/6 \rceil}{B} \right).$$

For $B = 8$: $k^* = \lceil 8/6 \rceil = 2$, $p_{k^*} = 2\pi \cdot 2/8 = \pi/2$,

$$m_{W,\min} = rB(1 - \cos(\pi/2)) = rB \cdot 1 = rB,$$

giving values 4.000, 8.000, 16.000 in Table 9 (for $r = 0.5, 1, 2$).

For $B = 16$: $k^* = \lceil 16/6 \rceil = 3$, $p_{k^*} = 2\pi \cdot 3/16 = 3\pi/8$,

$$m_{W,\min} = 16r(1 - \cos(3\pi/8)) \approx 16r \cdot 0.6173 \approx 9.877 r,$$

consistent with Table 9.

The doubler count is 20 for $B = 8$ and 44 for $B = 16$. The lattice momenta satisfying $\cos p_k < 1/2$ are $k \in \{2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$ for $B = 8$ (five values) and $k \in \{3, 4, \dots, 13\}$ for $B = 16$ (eleven values); with the fourfold spinor degeneracy this gives $4 \times 5 = 20$ and $4 \times 11 = 44$ respectively.

Figure 5: EXP 6: eigenvalue spectrum of the Wilson–Dirac operator (1D, $B = 16$, $N = 64$) for $r \in \{0.0, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0\}$. Top row: $U = 1$ (free field) with overlaid analytic eigenvalues $\lambda_{k,\pm}$ (open red circles; error $\varepsilon_{\text{an}} \sim 10^{-14}$). Bottom row: random $U \in U(1)$. The spectrum is symmetric about the real axis ($\lambda \in \text{spec}(D) \Rightarrow \bar{\lambda} \in \text{spec}(D)$, Remark 7.1). For $r = 0$: eigenvalues lie on the imaginary axis. For $r > 0$: doubler modes shift to the right (Wilson suppression, $m_{W,\text{min}} = rB(1 - \cos(2\pi \lceil B/6 \rceil / B))$).

10.9 EXP 7: Bit-Length Growth — Wilson–Dirac Operator vs RLWE Multiplication Chain

We compare bit-length growth in two iterative processes in the same ring $R_N = \mathbb{Z}[x]/(x^n + 1)$:

- **WD:** $\Psi_{k+1} = D_{W,U} \Psi_k$ (Wilson–Dirac operator, B sites, 4 spinor components),
- **RLWE:** $c_{k+1} = c_k \cdot a \pmod{x^n + 1}$ (iterated multiplication of a single ring element, analogous to noise propagation in ring-lattice-based cryptography).

The bit-length growth of the WD operator is consistently faster than the RLWE chain, by a factor of ≈ 1.3 – 1.8 at $k = 32$, depending on B and N :

- the ratio grows monotonically with B (for $N = 64$: 1.37 at $B = 32$, 1.70 at $B = 128$), because D multiplies by $B/2$ and sums over neighbours,
- the ratio decreases with N (for $B = 64$: 1.60 at $N = 64$, 1.32 at $N = 256$), because growth is distributed over more coefficients as $\varphi(N)$ increases.

Bit-length growth is asymptotically linear in k in both processes, confirming the regularity observed in EXP 5.

Table 10: EXP 7: growth of maximum bit-length for selected configurations (N, B) . Ratio = $\text{bl}_{\text{WD}}/\text{bl}_{\text{RLWE}}$.

N	B	k	bl_{WD}	bl_{RLWE}	ratio
64	32	1	9	6	1.50
64	32	8	50	36	1.39
64	32	32	194	142	1.37
64	64	1	10	6	1.67
64	64	8	58	36	1.61
64	64	32	226	141	1.60
64	128	1	11	6	1.83
64	128	8	66	38	1.74
64	128	32	258	152	1.70
128	64	1	10	7	1.43
128	64	8	58	39	1.49
128	64	32	226	156	1.45
256	64	1	10	7	1.43
256	64	8	58	42	1.38
256	64	32	226	171	1.32

Figure 6: EXP 7: growth of maximum bit-length in iterated applications of the Wilson–Dirac operator and the RLWE multiplication chain in the same ring $\mathbb{Z}[x]/(x^n + 1)$. WD growth is consistently faster by a factor of ≈ 1.3 – 1.8 .

11 Summary of Results

Table 11: Summary of key empirical results.

Property / measure	Result	Agreement
$E_{\text{arith}} = 0$ (SHA-256 hash)	PASS for all N	Thm. 5.2
$E_{\text{arith}} = 0$ (cross-platform)	bit-identical Win/Linux	Thm. 5.2
Covariance 1D	250/250	Thm. 6.1
Γ_5 -herm. 1D	250/250	Thm. 7.1
Negative tests 1D	500/500	Rem. 7.2
Covariance 2D	120/120	new result
Γ_5 -herm. 2D	120/120	new result
Negative tests 2D	240/240	new result
Slope mul. gen. (asympt.)	2.07	$\mathcal{O}(\varphi^2)$
Slope mul. mono. (asympt.)	0.98	$\mathcal{O}(\varphi)$
Scaling 1D	$T \sim B^{1.02}$	locality
Scaling 2D	$T \sim (B^2)^{1.00}$	locality
$E_{\text{gauge}} \sim \sin(\pi/N)$	slope 1.02	Thm. 8.1
$E_{\text{gauge}} \sim B$	slope 0.99	Thm. 8.1
Γ_5 -res. abs. (all r)	$\sim \varepsilon_{\text{mach}}$	Rem. 7.1
Agreement with analytic spectrum	$\varepsilon_{\text{an}} \sim 10^{-14}$	impl. correctness
$m_{W,\min}(B=8)$	rB	analytic formula
$m_{W,\min}(B=16)$	$\approx 9.877r$	analytic formula
Doubler count	20 ($B=8$), 44 ($B=16$)	$4 \times \{k : p_k > \pi/3\} $
Bitlen growth / step of D	≈ 7 bits	practical limitation
WD/RLWE bitlen ratio ($k=32$)	1.32–1.70	EXP 7, new result

12 Conclusions and Outlook

We have constructed a consistent Wilson–Dirac operator coupled to a discrete gauge field $G_N \subset U(1)$ over cyclotomic rings R_N , ensuring $E_{\text{arith}} = 0$ for operator evaluation. The experimental programme — encompassing structural validation in 1D and 2D (1110 positive and negative tests in total), asymptotic multiplication complexity analysis (range $N = 4 \dots 1024$, averaged over 3 seeds), spectral analysis with verification against the analytic free-field spectrum and analytic derivation of the doubler mass and count, and comparison of number-size growth with an RLWE multiplication chain — fully confirms the algebraic theorems. Independent reproduction on two platforms (Windows/Python 3.14.5 and Linux/Python 3.12) provides external confirmation of $E_{\text{arith}} = 0$.

Main conclusions:

1. **Algebraic.** Gauge covariance and Γ_5 -hermiticity hold exactly in the exact model, in both 1D and 2D. Negative tests confirm that the conditions (correct link transformation, real mass $\bar{m} = m$) are not only sufficient but also necessary.
2. **Complexity.** Asymptotic multiplication slopes (2.07 and 0.98) are consistent with theory. The small-size artefact (slopes underestimated for $\varphi \leq 8$) is explained by interpreter overhead.

3. **Spectral.** Γ_5 -hermiticity confirmed spectrally at machine precision ($\varepsilon_{\text{abs}} \sim \varepsilon_{\text{mach}}$) for all $r \in \{0, 0.5, 1, 2\}$ and both link configurations, using the correct Euclidean metric $|\lambda_j - \overline{\lambda_{k(j)}}|$. The minimal doubler mass and count are derived analytically from Brillouin zone geometry: $m_{W,\text{min}} = rB(1 - \cos(2\pi\lceil B/6\rceil/B))$, doubler count = $4 \cdot |\{k \in \{0, \dots, B-1\} : p_k > \pi/3\}|$. The free-field spectrum is reproduced with error $\sim 10^{-14}$.
4. **Practical.** Growth of ≈ 7 bits/step under iteration of D is a significant limitation for long iterations. Comparison with the RLWE chain shows growth is faster by a factor of 1.3–1.8 depending on B and N , strengthening the motivation to develop number-size control procedures.

Remark 12.1 (Future work). Priority directions:

- number-size control strategies: modular arithmetic / CRT, rescaling every k steps, requantisation back to $M_{s,N}$;
- low-level implementation (C/Numba) to reduce exact/numpy overhead ($\times 25$ – $\times 310$ depending on B , see Table 3);
- extension of validation to $d = 3, 4$;
- extension to non-abelian groups.

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